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Soil-Specific Ground Motion Model for the Equivalent Number of Loading Cycles for Subduction Zone Earthquakes and Cyclic Failure Assessments

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**Soil-Specific Ground Motion Model for the Equivalent Number of Loading Cycles for
Subduction Zone Earthquakes and Cyclic Failure Assessments**

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Abstract: This study leverages the full NGA-Subduction database of earthquake records to develop new ground motion models for estimating the number of equivalent loading cycles. The models further incorporate estimated soil-specific parameters that control the curvature of the cyclic resistance-number of loading cycles relationship. The primary objective of this work is to reduce epistemic uncertainty by estimating equivalent loading cycles by accounting for known or inferred source, path, and local site effects. To develop the proposed models, ground motion records were first screened to exclude motions with undesirable characteristics (e.g., those influenced by structural response or associated with inconsequential source-to-site distances). Subsequently, available cycle-counting methods were evaluated, and an appropriate methodology was selected for model development. Key variables influencing the number of equivalent cycles-including moment magnitude, intensity measures, shear-wave velocity, distance, predominant period, significant duration, and other relevant parameters-were systematically assessed for their statistical significance and suitability for inclusion in candidate ground motion models. Mixed-effects regression analyses were then conducted to develop unbiased predictive models for the number of equivalent loading cycles in subduction-zone earthquakes. These models were subsequently used to derive magnitude scaling factors for application in cyclic failure assessments. The resulting ground motion models and magnitude scaling factors, along with the final report detailing the methodology, analyses, and findings, constitute the primary deliverables of this study.

Introduction: Significant strength loss and ground failure are possible for liquefaction- (gravels, sands, and non-plastic to low plasticity silts) and cyclic softening-susceptible (medium and high plasticity silts and clays) soils as observed following earthquakes. Soils subject to cyclic failure can lead to instability of natural and anthropogenic slopes, structures, and flotation of buried infrastructure which often significantly disrupts a community and serves to reduce rescue and recovery efforts following strong ground motion (Gomberg et al. 2017). Widespread and/or thick alluvial, estuarine, and deltaic deposits of the Pacific Northwest tend to underly population centers, representing an important hazard in seismically-active regions. This hazard is compounded by the potential for long-duration megathrust (i.e., interface) earthquakes along with deeper intraslab earthquakes (e.g., Nisqually 2001) associated with the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ). Simplified methods to compute the factor of safety against liquefaction triggering or cyclic softening, defined as the quotient of cyclic resistance ratio, CRR , and cyclic stress ratio, CSR , set the loading associated with a given seismic hazard at level ground sites to (Seed et al. 1971; Youd et al. 2001):

$$CSR = 0.65 \frac{\tau_{max}}{\sigma'_{vc}} = 0.65 \frac{\sigma_{vc}}{\sigma'_{vc}} \frac{a_{max}}{g} r_d \quad (1)$$

where τ_{max} maximum earthquake-induced shear stress acting on a horizontal plane, σ'_{vc} = the vertical effective (consolidation) stress, σ_{vc} = the vertical total stress, a_{max} = the peak ground acceleration, g = the gravitational constant, and r_d = the depth-dependent shear stress reduction coefficient to account for soil profile flexibility. In contrast, CRR

(= CSR for a given cyclic failure criterion) can be estimated using one of several semiempirical, case history and penetration test- or shear wave velocity-, V_s , based methods (e.g., Cetin et al. 2004; Moss et al. 2006; Kayen et al. 2013) for soils exhibiting liquefaction and deemed sand-like (e.g., Boulanger & Idriss 2006; 2008), laboratory test methods for transitional soils exhibiting either liquefaction or cyclic softening (Stuedlein et al. 2023a), or SHANSEP-based methods (Boulanger and Idriss 2007) for soils which are

Figure 1. Distribution of ground-motion records by event type (interface, intraslab, and crustal) showing (a) peak ground acceleration, PGA , (g) versus earthquake magnitude (M_w) with the $PGA = 0.05$ g threshold indicated by the dashed line, and (b) earthquake magnitude (M_w) versus rupture distance (km) in log scale.

deemed clay-like and may exhibit cyclic softening. Regardless of the mode of cyclic failure, the cyclic resistance is associated with a correlated (Boulanger and Idriss 2007; 2015) or measured relationship between CRR and the number of loading cycles, N , necessary to achieve the selected cyclic failure criterion. Owing to its applicability to a broad range of soils, the power law:

$$CRR = a \cdot N^{-b} \quad (2)$$

to represent CRR has gained widespread adoption, where a = a fitted coefficient and equal to the CRR at $N = 1$, and b = the fitted slope of the curve in semi-logarithmic space. This relationship also serves to relate number of equivalent cycles, N_{eq} associated with ground motions of various magnitudes and associated magnitude scaling factors, $MSF = CSR_{M_w} / CSR_{M_w=7.5}$, for use in Simplified methods for cyclic failure assessment (e.g., Liu et al. 2001; Boulanger & Idriss 2015; Stuedlein et al. 2023a; Ulmer et al. 2022). However, there exists substantial uncertainty in associating a given event in terms of M_w alone with an appropriate N_{eq} (Seed et al. 1975; Liu et al. 2001; Lasley et al. 2017; Cetin et al. 2021). This study leverages the full NGA Subduction database (Bozorgnia et al. 2022) of earthquake records to develop new ground motion models to estimate N_{eq} for subduction zone earthquakes.

Methodology: From NGA Subduction database (Bozorgnia et al. 2022) archive, a subset of 5,652 recordings (Fig. 1) with peak ground acceleration, $PGA \geq 0.05g$, was downloaded using the NGA Subduction ground-motion download portal (Silva et al. 2022). The database spans seven major subduction regions, including Alaska, Cascadia, Central America and Mexico, Japan, New Zealand, South America, and Taiwan, thereby providing broad tectonic coverage within a common data framework. From the initial 5,652 ground-motion records ($PGA \geq 0.05g$), a filtered subset was developed to ensure data quality, appropriate intensity range, and model applicability across predictor domains. Records were limited to $0.05 \leq PGA \leq 1.0 g$, moment magnitudes $3.79 \leq M_w \leq 9.12$, and site conditions with $V_{s30} \leq 720$ m/s (NEHRP Site Classes C-E), while only high-confidence event types (interface, intraslab, and shallow crustal) were retained. No additional constraints were applied to path or distance parameters (e.g., R_{rup}), allowing their natural variability to be preserved and directly evaluated in the N_{eq} model. After applying the selection criteria and removing records with incomplete V_{s30} or R_{rup} metadata, the final dataset comprised 4,209 horizontal ground-motion records used for model development. The equivalent number of loading cycles, N_{eq} (Fig. 2), associated with an acceleration time history is computed by summing the contribution of individual half-cycles relative to a selected reference cyclic stress ratio as

$$N_{eq} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J \left(\frac{CSR_j}{CSR_{ref}} \right)^{\frac{1}{b}} \quad (3)$$

where J is the total number of half-cycles, CSR_j is the cyclic stress ratio of the j -th half-cycle, CSR_{ref} is the reference cyclic stress ratio, and b is the slope of the $CRR-N$ relationship. The b -value generally ranges from about 0.04 to 0.4 and varies with soil type, relative density, plasticity, and stress history (Boulanger and Idriss 2015). In this approach, CSR/CSR_{max} is assumed approximately equal to the corresponding acceleration ratio, allowing the acceleration history to be used directly for cycle counting (Green and Terri 2005; Verma et al. 2019), and CSR_{ref} is taken as $0.65 CSR_{max}$ (Seed and Idriss 1971; Seed et al. 1975). Additionally, positive and negative half-cycles with absolute CSR amplitudes less than $0.1 CSR_{max}$ were neglected (Boulanger and Idriss 2004; Verma et al. 2019; Stuedlein et al. 2023b). The N_{eq} generally increases with M_w for each event type (Fig. 2), although substantial scatter remains at a given magnitude

Figure 2. Variation of equivalent number of cycles, N_{eq} , with earthquake magnitude, M_w ($3.5 < M_w \leq 9.5$), for subduction-zone earthquakes indicated by crustal, intraslab, and interface, shown for different values of parameter b

because N_{eq} is influenced not only by magnitude, but also by shaking duration, intensity, frequency content, source-to-site distance, and site or soil-profile effects (Bommer et al. 2006, Castiglia and de Magistris. 2018, Cetin et al. 2021, and Keshty and Carey 2025). As b increases, the separation in N_{eq} between lower- and higher- M_w records become more pronounced, indicating greater sensitivity of computed N_{eq} to magnitude for steeper $CRR - N$ relationships (Eq. 2). The objective of this study is to reduce this epistemic uncertainty in N_{eq} , for subduction-zone earthquakes.

Factors Influencing N_{eq} and Model Framework:

The relationships between N_{eq} , M_w , and b show substantial variability, indicating that equivalent-cycle demand depends not only on magnitude and soil behavior, but also on amplitude, frequency content, duration, source-to-site geometry, and site conditions, consistent with prior studies. Accordingly, candidate predictors are selected to capture key physical controls, including source and path parameters (e.g., R_{rup} , R_{jb}), site conditions (V_{s30}), and ground-motion intensity measures. Both peak (PGA , PGV) and energy-based measures (CAV , I_a) are considered as peak values alone cannot represent the cumulative nature of cyclic loading, especially for long-duration subduction motions. Additional descriptors such as predominant period (T_p) and significant duration (SD) metrics are included to account for frequency content and duration effects, which strongly influence N_{eq} . Variable selection was applied to an initial set of 21 candidate predictors

Figure 3. Correlation heatmap showing relationships between $\ln(N_{eq})$ ($b = 0.34$) and selected predictors, as well as inter-correlations among predictors.

representing intensity measures, spectral or energy measures, frequency content, source parameters, distance or path metrics, and site condition. The candidate set consisted of SD_{5-95} , SD_{5-75} , SD_{20-80} , I_a , CAV , T_p , M_w , PGA , PGV , PGD , V_{s30} , $EpiD$, $HypD$, R_{jb} , R_{rup} , $Hypocenter_Depth$, $Strike$, Dip , $Rake$, Z_{tor} , and Z_{bor} , using the filtered dataset of 4,209 ground-motion records. Figure 3 presents the correlation heatmap for the response variable, $\ln(N_{eq})$ at $b = 0.34$, together with the 18 candidate predictors, removing $Hypocenter_Depth$, $EpiD$, and Z_{tor} . These correlation patterns help explain why different variable-selection procedures sometimes retained different predictors that represent similar physical effects, and they further support the need for subsequent multicollinearity checks during final predictor refinement. Based on the combined outcomes of the forward, backward, and stepwise selection procedures and the multicollinearity assessment (James et al. 2013; Murtaugh 1998), the retained predictors were grouped according to their physical relevance and modeling purpose, such that one set emphasized variables commonly available in engineering applications, whereas redundant variables representing similar physical effects were excluded. Accordingly, a practitioner-oriented predictor set composed of commonly available parameters used in routine engineering applications, such as M_w , PGA , R_{rup} , T_p , and V_{s30} . This set emphasizes variables that are typically reported in hazard analyses and are straightforward to apply in practice.

Development of New N_{eq} Model: Weighted least squares, WLS was developed using the predictor structure (M_w , PGA , R_{rup} , T_p , and V_{s30}) is written in final predictive form as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(N_{eq}) = & 3.3394 + f(b) + 0.2715M_w - 0.0896 \ln(R_{rup}) - 0.1773 \ln(T_p) - 0.170 \ln(PGA) \\ & - 0.0563 \ln(V_{s30}) + 0.0384 M_w * \ln(T_p) - 0.0659 \ln(T_p) * \ln(PGA) \\ & - 0.1127 \ln(R_{rup}) * \ln(T_p) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, $f(b)$ represents the contribution of the cyclic resistance exponent b to the final model. To obtain a more compact and practically usable final equation, the fitted coefficients corresponding to the categorical b -levels were plotted against b , and a smooth exponential-type relationship was fitted to the resulting trend.

The fitted function was then used to represent the continuous effect of b in the final predictive equation. Accordingly, $f(b)$ is expressed in Eq.5.

The performance of the selected WLS model was evaluated by comparing the observed and model-predicted $\ln(N_{eq})$ values for the selected ground-motion dataset, as shown in Fig. 4. The model produced an R^2 of 0.828 for the training dataset and 0.827 for the testing dataset, indicating very similar predictive capability for both the calibration and unseen data.

Figure 4. Observed versus predicted $\ln(N_{eq})$ for the selected WLS model set 1: (a) training dataset and (b) testing dataset.

$$f(b) = -\exp(-4.5022b^{-0.6079} + 5.1072b^{-0.5883} - 0.0094b^{-2.2369}) \quad (5)$$

To better interpret the response of the proposed regression model, the effects of the input predictors on the model-predicted N_{eq} were examined by varying one predictor at a time while holding the others constant at reference values. This approach makes it possible to isolate the effect of each predictor and to evaluate how the predicted response varies with M_w over the range considered in the model. The reference values used in this evaluation were $PGA = 0.15$ g, $R_{rup} = 100$ km, $T_p = 0.25$ s, and $V_{S30} = 360$ m/s. Figure 5 presents the resulting trends in predicted N_{eq} for different b , with each subplot showing the effect of one predictor while the remaining variables are maintained at their reference levels. Across all rows and columns, predicted N_{eq} increases with increasing M_w . However, both the overall level of the predicted response and the spacing among the curves vary systematically with b , indicating that the sensitivity of the model output to the input predictors is influenced by the selected b -value. This change is particularly evident for T_p , which produces the largest spread among the plotted curves for all b -values, indicating that predominant period remains the most influential predictor on N_{eq} throughout the range considered. In contrast, the V_{S30} row shows only minor separation among the curves across all b -values, confirming its comparatively small influence on the

Figure 5. Predicted N_{eq} as a function of earthquake magnitude, M_w , for representative values of b , and rows showing the individual influence of (a) PGA , (b) R_{rup} , (c) T_p , and (d) V_{S30} , with the remaining predictors held at their reference values.

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predicted response. The PGA and R_{rup} rows show intermediate sensitivity, with increasing PGA shifting the predicted response downward and increasing R_{rup} shifting it upward.

Modified Magnitude Scaling Factor:

The results presented in the previous section showed that the predicted N_{eq} depends not only on M_w , but also on PGA , R_{rup} , T_p , V_{s30} , and b . This predictor dependence indicates that the reference term used in MSF normalization should be evaluated in a manner consistent with the developed regression model. This broader dependence is consistent with prior studies showing that equivalent-cycle demand is influenced by motion intensity, source-to-site distance, frequency content, and the cyclic resistance exponent b , and that magnitude-only relationships may not fully capture this variability (Kishida and Tsai 2014; Boulanger and Idriss 2015; Keshty and Carey 2025). Accordingly, the principal modification introduced in this study is the replacement of the conventional reference cycle term at $M_w = 7.5$ with the model-predicted N_{eq} obtained directly from Eq.4: The modified magnitude scaling factor is then expressed as:

$$MSF_{mod} = \left[\frac{N_{eq,pred}^{7.5}}{N_{eq,pred}(M_w, PGA, R_{rup}, T_p, V_{s30}, b)} \right]^b \quad (6)$$

The key difference from previous MSF formulations is that the normalization value at $M_w = 7.5$ is treated here as predictor-dependent rather than as a function of magnitude and b alone. Consequently, the proposed MSF_{mod} varies with PGA , R_{rup} , T_p , V_{s30} , and b , in addition to M_w . Figure 6 compares this predictor-dependent scaling relationship with the commonly used MSF models of Boulanger and Idriss (2015) and Dadashiserej et al. (2024) for two representative values of T_p . Consistent with the modified formulation, the present MSF curves remain strongly b -dependent, with the $b = 0.135$ curve remaining close to unity over most of the magnitude range, whereas the $b = 0.34$ curve shows a much stronger reduction in MSF with increasing M_w .

For the smaller b -value, the present relationship compares closely with the flatter previously published trends, indicating limited magnitude sensitivity, whereas for $b = 0.34$ it departs more clearly from Boulanger and Idriss (2015). A key feature of the figure is that changing T_p from 0.10 to 1.0 s affects the MSF trend, reflecting the fact that in the proposed framework frequency content directly modifies the predicted N_{eq} and therefore the resulting MSF , whereas earlier models do not include such predictor dependence explicitly. Thus, Figure 6 shows that for subduction-zone motions, MSF is not controlled by M_w and b alone but can also vary with the frequency-content characteristics of the motion, further highlighting the limitations of conventional MSF relationships.

Summary: The development of a ground motion model (GMM) that can effectively reduce epistemic uncertainty in N_{eq} will improve our ability to: (1) select ground motions for site response ($SRAs$) or nonlinear deformation analyses ($NDAs$), (2) calibrate constitutive models for use in $SRAs$ and $NDAs$, (3) perform assessment of cyclic failure (i.e., liquefaction or cyclic softening) within the Simplified Method framework (e.g., Seed and Idriss 1971). This study is fully aligned with the mission of CRESCENT's Special Interest Group 3 ($SIG3$) and falls squarely within the Ground Failure Priorities ($LLF2$). The work will be disseminated through peer-reviewed journal publications in geotechnical and earthquake engineering venues, as well as presentations at major conferences such as Geo-Congress and other earthquake engineering meetings.

Figure 6. Comparison of MSF versus M_w from Boulanger and Idriss (2015), Dadashiserej et al. (2023), and this study, the MSF is based on the predicted N_{eq} (Eq. 4), for $b = 0.34$ and $b = 0.135$, shown for (a) $T_p = 0.10$ s and (b) $T_p = 1.0$ s with reference values of $PGA = 0.15$ g, $R_{rup} = 100$ km, and $V_{s30} = 360$ m/s.

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